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What is a Sustainable Curriculum?

Re-thinking the Modes of Curricular Existence

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ABSTRACT

The following intervention proposes an alternative way of thinking about curricula. It argues that current theorizing about curricula tends to confuse sustainable course contents with a sustainable curriculum. Drawing on object-oriented ontology and actor network theory it offers a way of rethinking curricula to better attend to the real challenge of sustainability.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Sustainability and Engineering Education, Ethics and Engineering Education

Keywords: Sustainability, Curriculum Theory, Object Oriented Ontology

INTRODUCTION

Rethinking curricula from an ecological point of view demands much more than merely adding courses on sustainability-related themes. It requires a revision of the way that we think about the nature of curricula, an open reconceptualization of what a curriculum might be.

Almost all thinking on curricula, like so much else that is inherited from the western tradition, is rooted in an idealized conception of the human being which sees minds as separate from the world that surrounds them. Humans are not entangled in things, they are not part of the world or an ecosystem. They are radically separated into mind and body, or, at another level, into society and nature, or the study of discourse and the study of things. This mode of thinking supports what might be called superficially sustainable curricular reform. The superficially sustainable engineering school has modules on sustainable manufacturing, it has researchers working on producing green energy, classes on sustainable cities, and so forth. In accordance with broadly accepted ideas about how to form a sustainable curriculum, the teachers at this school work across disciplines, making a consistent effort to make students aware of environmental problems. [1] In addition to course work, students at this school find themselves immersed in a culture which reinforces and generates sustainable values. The school conforms to the definition of a sustainable curriculum offered by the UK Engineering Council and other such organizations. In other words, it fosters an “understanding of the requirement for engineering activities to promote sustainable development”. [2] We should be happy such schools exist. However, if this is our

paradigm for a sustainable curriculum, then we have a major sustainability problem. Why?

*One can intend to teach about sustainability, without that curriculum being sustainable. Between the intention to teach something and its enactment, **there are always material conditions that intervene to make that happening of the curriculum possible. These conditions, despite the strain that it may place on our traditional ways of thinking, need to be seen as part of the curriculum.** Rather than asking whether the courses are about sustainability, we need to explore whether the entire network of material parts and multi-agent interactions making those courses possible is consistent with sustaining life on earth.* Every sustainable development curriculum implies classrooms, books, computers, and other supports proximate and distant, including connections to various infrastructures and networks—including intercontinental fiber optic cables, highway systems, global markets, and power grids. This is true for brick and mortar institutions and for digital classrooms. These supports form part of the indispensable conditions of existence for any curriculum; these material networks *are also the curriculum.*

Reflecting on curricular sustainability in this broader sense is challenging, because it undercuts the legitimacy of the model of sustainability thinking presented above. Our superficially sustainable curriculum involved lessons transmitted by textbooks. Books are made of paper, and that paper comes from trees, which in turn come from forests. These forests might be managed sustainably... or they might not be. In most cases, neither of these things will be transparently evident to students reading about the benefits of reducing, reusing, and recycling. Say we replace books with computers or digitized documents of some kind. We often think that digital documents are more sustainable than paper ones, we feel like we are doing something environmentally virtuous when we do not print out a document but rather consult it electronically. But also means that we overlook the material reality of computing. What is a computer? It is rare that we think deeply about this question, because most of the time we do not look at or into our computers, but rather through them, considering only the information that they contain. [3] Yet as anyone who has ever seen Edward Burtynsky's photos of e-waste recycling sites in China would know, computers are much more than streams of information. They are generally made of plastic (a petroleum by-product) filled with various pieces of silicon and rare metals, some of which are non-toxic and recyclable, others of which are toxic, non-recyclable, and frankly dangerous for human health. [4] Many of these materials are sourced or disposed of in ways that are neither sustainable nor humane (consider the case of coltan, one of the key materials employed in the making of smartphones, and the cause of a great deal of violence against both human beings and the environment). [5] A computer is always either immediately or via radio waves attached to two cable systems, one of which brings it power (the source of which may well be combusting coal), another one distant information. This latter implies links to fiber optic systems and server farms world-wide, all of which once again consume potentially non-sustainable energy sources, while potentially (in the case of undersea cables) interfering in marine ecosystems. [6] To these considerations we can also include reflections on the sources of heat and light in the classroom, or the means of transportation by which students come to and from their homes or dorms to the classrooms.

Wholly other sets of connections also inflect the real sustainability of a classroom and ought to be taken into account. These connections are not primarily material like the ones mentioned about, but include socio-material networks like the economy.

Everyone knows that schooling is expensive. Top schools need to have significant funds to enact their curricula (and to compete for places on the Shanghai ranking). But where does this money come from? We can safely assume that the sustainability of the tuition money in elite schools will roughly mirror the sustainability of the sources of high-income employment within society. It is mostly the parents' jobs or the student's downstream employments which will generate the revenues that cover tuition fees. Given that so many of the world's largest and richest corporations are unsustainable (four out of the top five grossing corporations worldwide are petroleum or energy companies) we can conclude that at least part of the money paying for the happening of any curriculum is unsustainable (the case is only slightly altered in the case of public school systems, since the wealthiest corporations pay the most taxes.) Aside from student tuitions, most major universities derive their funds from endowments and research contracts with corporations and governments. Are these funds sustainable? The recent student movements protesting the high percentage of fossil fuel stocks in the portfolios of many top American universities show that this not yet the case. [7] What about the research contracts? It is more than likely that any top engineering school with some courses on sustainable development will also have researchers working on projects funded by the fossil fuel industry, with it being no stretch of the imagination that these are *the same researchers* teaching courses on sustainability. As Naomi Klein and others have shown, highly visible investing in sustainability research has been one of the most frequently used greenwashing strategies deployed by major companies in the petroleum and transport industries. [8] Of course, one can reply to this analysis that the material contribution of unsustainable industry to increasing sustainability actually amounts to a net demonstration that the curriculum is sustainable, since investments are flowing from the unsustainable to the sustainable. But what one cannot do is disregard this level of complexity when considering curricula.

The economic does not exhaust the complexity of curricula, however, particularly if we are thinking about engineering schools. Unlike liberal arts institutions, engineering students spend a great deal of time interacting with technological devices. Whether these be robots, computers, or nanoscale microscopes, engineering schools would not exist without technologies. Based on the above we might be tempted to analyze the sustainability of these technologies via purely material considerations. But if we did so, we would miss out on what might be called their architectural telos. This is a twofold category, one with respect to how technologies condition us, and one with respect to how the current design of a technology conditions future redesigns of the same. Both aspects come into play when we consider the direction in which any curriculum is likely to evolve, and both aspects can to be considered part of the sustainability of an engineering curriculum. *The design of current technologies impacts the design of future technologies and so plays a role in the sustainability of a curriculum.*

It turns out that assessing or even describing sustainable curriculum is harder than making up a curriculum about sustainability. The examples that I have given are not exhaustive but rather suggestive of the real complexity of curricula. Serious attempts to think about the sustainability of engineering curricula must not flee from this complexity but rather embrace it. Doing so poses conceptual and methodological challenges, may leave us feeling lost or confused, may seem to alienate us from what we thought was reasonable and certain. But failing to even attempt to rise to the challenge or brushing aside the concerns raised by deeper questions are sure recipes for failure.

1 RETHINKING CURRICULA

1.1 A Curriculum as an Enacted Ecosystem

A sustainable curriculum possesses the long-term means for its perpetuation. A curriculum that is sustainable is sustainable on all levels, not just sufficiently sustainable to reassure us that we are trying to do something at the level of ideas. Thinking about curriculum that overlooks the question of long-term means by focusing only on ideas and pedagogical intentions is endemic, and this is precisely what we have criticized in the standard model conception of ecological curricula. In order to avoid shallow thinking, we must *view curricula from the point of view of their enactment as opposed to their content*. By enactment we intent the broader coming into being of a curriculum. This means that we abandon the subject-centered intentional understanding of curriculum that is and has been the norm. We must now consider the interactions between all of the things involved in making happen a curriculum as we normally intend the word. Material things, and not just human intenders are now actors. A curriculum is a particular kind of complex ecosystem, and it can be studied as one studies other ecosystems, albeit with an addition of the additional complexity introduced by the importance of intention and discourse in human interactions.

This is obviously a heterodox interpretation of the meaning of curriculum, though it is not an abusive one, even from the viewpoint of etymology. According to the *Oxford Latin Dictionary*, the word *curriculum* (a 2nd declension neuter noun) has the following definitions: the “act of running,” the “chariot,” the “course of action/heavenly bodies”, “lap, track,” and “race.” [9] Roughly half of these meanings refer to the aspect of the curriculum that interests us, namely the material conditions or the ecosystem in which the race occurs—the chariot and the track—and their influence on the happening of the race.

1.2 Anti-Anthropocentrism

Recent work philosophy in the philosophy of the social sciences, has suggested that we must move away from understanding society anthropocentrically. [10,11] Anti-anthropocentrism in this sense implies that we must not overly privilege what social actors think that they are doing when we analyze what happens in social groups. Our ideas and intentions are merely one level in the complex tangle of interactions that make up any kind of social happening. A computer, a test bench, or the geographic location of a school, can thus be thought of as equally important to the happening of a curriculum as the ideas of a pedagogical visionary like MIT’s William Barton Rogers. A curriculum is thus not just the sequence in which ideas and values are impressed upon human minds, nor any accounting that might be made of those ideas and values, but something much more complex and indeed ambiguous. Our example above illustrates this perfectly: is our curriculum sustainable or not? Yes and no, depending upon which perspective we privilege. One is tempted to eliminate one or the other aspects just to get a clear response. Yet a better reaction is to think about a way to create a meaningful discourse about this complexity, to find out a way of making sense of and attending to the complex and conflicting aspects and actors at work within the unfolding of curricula.

1.3 Theory versus Topography

We tend not to appreciate the complexity of things in part because so much of human practice is aimed at reducing complexity. Theories attempt to reduce complex happenings to simpler structures or essences that are taken to be the real of what initially appeared complex. They are intrinsically reductive. But what we need is not reduction but orientation. We need tools that encourage us to look a bit farther, to find out what is around the next bend, to prompt us to fill in details and aspects of curricula that we might otherwise miss. One method of preserving complexity while orienting ourselves within this complexity is cartographical or topographical. Topographies do

simplify to provide orientation, but they in no way suggest that the map is more real than the territory. The rewards for employing this kind of topographical approach involve greater sensitivity to difference and complexity, as well as a heightened understanding of the mereological relations between the curriculum and its constituent elements.

Because a curriculum is highly complex, involving mind-mind interactions, mind-object interactions, and object-object interactions, as well as variable dimensions of expression and latency, multiple degrees of conscious and unconscious awareness, fairly complicated metaphysical notions are necessary for its description. I therefore introduce the notion of the mode of existence. A mode of existence is a way of being that is complete but not total or exclusive. By this I mean that that mind-object interactions exist on a different plane than mind-mind interactions, that these interactions have play out along what seem to be independent lines of temporality, spatiality, and causality, and that both interactional nexuses are to be treated as equally real, precisely because the interactions between these two modes must both exist, and exist ambiguously. Understanding a curriculum involves elaborating its topography across multiple modes of existence.

In order to illustrate my point, we can consider abstractly the idea of the sustainable curriculum and its material reality. In terms of mind-mind interactions, all of the teachers and students might well believe that a curriculum is sustainable, without that curriculum being as sustainable as they think in object-object terms. As Etienne Souriau has pointed out, a typical theoretical gesture is to attempt to assign degrees of reality to the varying existential modes, essentially claiming that some are less real than others. [12] Yet just as it would be violent and even absurd to say to a depressed person that their perceived causes of their sadness were unreal, and that the real source of their depression is their serotonin levels, it is violent and absurd to claim any aspect of the curriculum as the real. Every mode of existence is characterized by a specific articulation of how actants can relate meaningfully with one another. It would be wholly possible (if contrafactual) to imagine that a curriculum was materially sustainable without anyone having ever intended this to be the case, just as it was the case that the curriculum that we initially imagined sustainable turned out not to be so, though the long-term evolution of both curricula would be different (but that would depend upon more factors than just the intention to make a sustainable curriculum).

2 FOUR MODES OF EXISTENCE

Contemporary philosopher Graham Harman has introduced a fourfold existential topography that can help us to direct our attention to the broad modal outlines of curricular existence. [13] I say broad outlines, because as we will see, every fundamental mereological framework (and that is to say every science, be it chemistry, physics, or curriculum studies) establishes a novel mode of existence as it codes meaningful elements within its discursive system. Nevertheless, Harman's work is interesting because of its relatively high level of ontological abstraction allows us to rediscover its broad outlines in other, more local, existential ontologies.

Harman calls the four primary modes of existence the "fourfold." According to Harman the fourfold is made up of two pairs, each of which is in tension with its other. [14] The first pair of modes he calls real objects and their qualities, and the second pair are sensual objects and their qualities. Rather than adumbrating the sense that he attributes to these terms, it seems more useful to introduce and explain the versions of these notions adapted to the study of curriculum. In what follows, I equate the

Harman's distinction between the real object and its qualities with the metaphysical and the material curriculum, while the distinction between the sensual object and its qualities are equated with the social and the subjective curriculum.

2.1 Metaphysical Curriculum

The **metaphysical curriculum** exists in a state that Harman describes as "withdrawn." It is primarily to be understood as a group of objects subtracted from their relations. These objects include both human beings and material things like buildings or books. No subject experiences or perceives this curriculum directly, no two objects interact with one another. No science or discourse about this curriculum is possible. The metaphysical curriculum in this sense is latent and remains latent, but it is the site from which all radical curricular becomings originate. It is at once a pure idea and the bedrock of material reality.

If we thus have nothing to say about the metaphysical curriculum, why then should we even mention it here? Most importantly, claiming that there is such a metaphysical curriculum affirms that there is a reality out there, a reality wholly independent from the human mind and the constructions of discourse, and that beings have a reality apart from those expressed in their relations. Stipulating an outside allows also for us to theoretically leave space for becoming, and to recognize non-human material agency. It can also, and likewise, be thought provide a metaphysical justification for the exercise of the principle of precaution as it is elaborated in the philosophy of Hans Jonas. [15]

2.2 The Material Curriculum

The material curriculum corresponds, in Harman's thought, to what he calls the real qualities of an object, and we can understand this to be the curriculum insofar as it is expressed in object/object interactions. Contrary to the metaphysical curriculum, the material curriculum is expressed (if it is not necessarily expressed to human observers). We might thus speak of it as available to science, but not necessarily present to science, and of course never present to science in precisely the same form that any discourse about this science might take. In fact, any account of the material mode will only be partial, only offered to knowing subjects through the mediation of a system of discourse and practices. Actor Network Theory-influenced science studies scholars have often—and with good reason—discussed material modes of existence as multiple. As Anne Marie Mol has illustrated, after having carefully studied production of knowledge and discourse around the material aspects of the patient's bodies within a hospital, via the study of blood chemistry, or cell cultures, or radiographic images, we end up having multiple bodies, since each technically assisted process offers insight into an aspect of the material that can only with difficulty be translated into terms equivalent with another. [16] This is because each mode of making discourse implies different material connections relative to the coming to discourse among objects. Let us note also that human bodies are also deeply entangled in the material curriculum. This is true in the sense that human bodies are involved in making sense of matter, but also in the sense that human bodies are affected by matter in ways that oftentimes elude or challenge sense making. It has been shown, for example, that chemicals emitted into the air by automobiles affect the development of children's cognitive functioning, leading to higher incidences of learning disorders and including ADHD. [17] As is evident, having affected children in the classroom, or, considering a larger time frame—affected teachers behind the lecterns—will affect the contents and the rhythm of the courses taught within an institution. But making sense of these changes, at least from a first-person point of view, must remain obscure. None of the people that are affected know what life would be like outside of their being affected. All would be

affected differently by this differently were they aware of these material interactions. How they understand their being affected happens through a process of translation, via a making sense of one regime of signs (reflective personal experience) in terms of another regime of signs (scientific knowledge about brain chemistry). In a practical sense, describing a curriculum in terms of the material curriculum involves looking for spaces that can be measured, but which stands outside any accounting of human social actors regarding either their individual or collective intentions and understandings.

2.3 The Social Curriculum

The social curriculum is the curriculum as it exists in mental, social, or inter-subjective space. It is not necessarily the curriculum as it is consciously articulated by actors, but rather the unconscious within the discourses produced by conscious actors, or at least between actors interacting via sign systems. Within the social curriculum we can situate what some have called the “invisible” or “hidden” curriculum, we can also situate many of the dimensions of the curriculum brought out by Structuralist curriculum scholars such as Bernstein. [18] The social curriculum does not exclude the material, but includes the socio-material tangle that is the economy, as well as what Bruno Latour has called the Parliament of Things, namely the articulate results of human-non-human interactions such as scientific disciplines, as well as various phenomena associated with material signification. [19, 20] It can also include the symbolic, but unintentional meaning of various object dispositions, such as the meaning of chairs in a room or departments within campus buildings. The key feature of this curricular mode from the point of view of scholars striving to establish curricular topographies is its distance from the intentions of the actors involved in articulating it, it is thus available to what systems theorist and sociologist Niklas Luhmann calls second order observers. [21] For many, this is the most interesting dimension in curricular studies. Within this framework can discuss elements such as the effects of an environmental studies professor’s gas guzzling car on the lessons that he or she teaches, or study the ways in which Judeo-Christian ideas about the natural world structure the environmental values conveyed by an institution. It should be noted that just as in the case of the modes of material existence, each of these networks of connections within the social curricular mode of existence appears ontologically discrete, since they can only come to subjectivity through a specific process of enactment and translation. This means that we can look at the same social curriculum from the point of view of economic relations or gender relations, and both will yield insights into the sustainability of a curriculum, but neither will articulate in the same way the elements within the social curriculum. A topographic approach allows these various perspectives to co-exist and to co-inform our understanding of curricular sustainability.

2.4 The Subjective Curriculum

It may seem almost unnecessary to discuss the subjective curriculum, because it is this curriculum that has historically almost always been the subject of discussions on curriculum. The subjective curriculum is the *content* of a curriculum as it is articulated by a conscious subject aiming to construct a plan for teaching students. The subjective curriculum includes the visions of curriculum articulated by educators and administrators, not in their textuality or material reality, but as they themselves believe that they understand them. It also includes the signification of all the curricular supports and events—books, exams, even the symbolic importance of campus monuments—but seen only from the viewpoint of the educator’s intentions. More broadly speaking, and this is crucial for understanding the interest of the multi-modal model presented here, the subjective curriculum is any version of the curriculum that any subject—a

teacher, a student, or a curriculum scholar—articulates. In the final instance, this therefore also includes any account of an institution's curriculum articulated by a scholar, including one using the methods here. That said, there is obviously a radical practical difference between considering the subjective curriculum as the total extent of the curriculum—i.e. speaking of a curricular vision or an intent to articulate a specific curricular vision—and recognizing that it is just the tip of the curricular iceberg.

3 Towards a Conclusion

The elements presented here prompt us to more fully describe the elements in existing curricula, but they do not explain how to form a sustainable curriculum. What then is the point of this exercise?

3.1 Studying Curricula

The general topographical oriented presented is really aimed at those seeking to carefully and scientifically describe curricula. This is important, since to a certain degree we cannot understand what our curricula are without carefully applying ourselves to this task. Considering each mode of existence in turn it forces us to explore the potential importance of that which may not appear to have meaning to the traditional curriculum theorist. This brings about a second benefit, namely the fact that a multimodal approach offers a richer sense of the meaning and lessons enacted by a particular curriculum. The key here is to note that unlike traditional thinking on curriculum, where one supposes that each institution has a single curriculum, this approach allows us to envision multiple and sometimes apparently contradictory curricula existing within the same institution. While paying attention to these additional levels of complexity may seem frustrating, it is crucial to note that it is only by acknowledging complexity can we hope to improve curricular sustainability.

3.2 Pedagogy for Sustainable Innovations

Assuming that we have taken the time to appreciate curriculum in all of its complexity, what do we do next? The first thing to do is recognize that we have already undergone an essential re-orientation—we are now operating not from ideas down, but from material signs on up. Deeply engaging with the material curriculum in all of its levels will yield ecological awareness, but it may also yield innovations. Solutions to environmental problems do not come out of thin air, but rather out of an everyday entanglement with environmental problems. The more profoundly our curricula set in motion processes of co-creation in which actors human and non-human engage with one another, the greater the likelihood that our curriculum actually tends towards being sustainable and producing sustainability innovators.

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